

INTERFACE-CORRELATED BONDING PROPERTIES OF A ROLL BONDED AL-CU SHEET

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1 Introduction

Al-Cu bimetal plates exhibit excellent exclusive properties such as reduced weight, formability and corrosion resistance without much expense of electrical conductivity as compared to monolithic pure copper or copper alloys [1]. This materials combination is also economically more attractive than monolithic Cu when the fabricating process for this bimetal is economically competitive like roll bonding adopted in this study. However, it is difficult to bond dissimilar metals such as Al and Cu using warm roll bonding followed by typical annealing, because brittle and harmful intermetallic compound (IMC) phases such as AlCu and Al₃Cu₄ are easily generated at elevated temperatures [2-4]. Therefore, it is necessary for Al/Cu combination to control initial stage of roll bonding parameter to the exclusion of post-annealing and it is important to study effect of rolling strain on the interface and overall mechanical properties of an Al/Cu 2-ply laminate. In the present study, the influence of reduction ratio during roll bonding between Al and Cu alloys on the microstructural evolution and subsequent mechanical properties of Al/Cu laminated composite was investigated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Roll bonding of parent alloys

Commercial aluminum alloy AA1050 and pure copper (UNS C 11000) sheets were selected as component of the laminated alloys. After proper surface treatment by brushing and degreasing, sheet materials with a dimension of 375 mm in width and ~500 mm in length were subjected to roll bonding with different reduction ratio of 65, 50 and 30%, as summarized in Table 1. Initial thickness of aluminum alloy was differently prepared in order to obtain ~3 mm thick Al/Cu 2-ply laminated

composites having the similar final thickness ratio of Al:Cu as ~8:1.

Al: heating (~380 °C) Cu: room temp.	Reduction ratio, %	Final thickness of 2-ply, mm
Sample # 1	65	3.05
Sample # 2	50	3.21
Sample # 3	30	2.80

Table 1. Target reduction ratio and thickness of Al/Cu 2-ply sheets

2.2 Characterization

Transmission electron microscope (TEM, model JEOL JEM-2100F) at 200 kV was used to examine the interfaces of Al/Cu joints. Uniaxial tensile tests were conducted using an Instron 8862 testing machine at an initial strain rate of 10⁻³ s⁻¹ at room temperature. Flat dog-bone tensile specimens (ASTM standard E8M-01) with gage length of 20 mm were prepared along the direction parallel to the transverse direction (TD) of the sheet materials. After cutting 2-ply clad plate with a width of 20 mm and a length above 300 mm, bonding strength of the Al/Cu laminated sheet was measured by roller drum-type peel test (standard ASTM D3167). In addition, a series of three-point bending tests was performed to figure out interface crack initiation and propagation under the transverse loading which indicates the bend axis was perpendicular to the rolling direction.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Interface microstructure

Fig. 1(a)~1(c) show the bright-field TEM images at the bonding interface between Al and Cu from as-rolled samples #1, #2, and #3, respectively. There is

a discontinuously generated reaction phase ranging from 50 to 100 nm in thickness in Fig. 1(a). The outlets of Fig. 1(a) illustrate the selected area diffraction patterns from both diffusive interface and constituent alloys of sample #1, in which the narrow diffusive interlayer can be indexed as Al_4Cu_9 IMC phase. In the specimen #2 processed for roll bonding under the reduction ratio of 50 %, as presented in Fig. 1(b), Al layer contains a homogeneously elongated lamellar structure with several internal voids adjacent to the interface between parent alloys. However, in the Al/Cu laminated composite roll bonded under the lowest reduction ratio of 30%, the microstructure of Al layer mostly consists of the equiaxed sub- μm grains together with internal voids as shown in Fig. 1(c). This indicates that microstructural changes of both the parent alloy and the interface are strongly affected by the amount of shear strain induced by roll bonding, which is controlled in terms of reduction ratio.

Fig. 1. Bright-field TEM images obtained close to the bonding interface of (a) Al/Cu 2-ply sample #1, (b) sample #2, and (c) sample #3.

3.2 Mechanical properties

Fig. 2(a) shows true tensile stress-strain curves of the roll bonded Al/Cu 2-ply composites, where the effect of reduction ratio on the uniaxial tensile properties is presented. The stress-strain curve for the sample #1 reaches a maximum stress at an elongation of 17%, followed by a fairly short stage exhibiting two-step stress drop. It is interesting to note here that tensile strength of the 2-ply composite become obviously poor as the reduction ratio during roll bonding decreases. The effectiveness of roll bonding on the improvement of elongation is also clearly shown in Fig. 2(a). Therefore strong

metallurgical bonding for 2-ply sample #1 by the generation of thin, less harmful Al_4Cu_9 intermetallic compound layer, whose thickness is less than 100 nm, leads to improved tensile elongation. According to the fracture macrostructure from tensile test specimens in Fig. 2(b), first stress drop phenomena for the 2-ply clad sheets in Fig. 2(a) were obviously caused by the initiation of fracture from constituent Cu part, while the second stage of stress drop corresponded to the necking followed by fracture from remaining Al side, regardless of the reduction ratio.

Fig. 2. (a) True stress-strain curves for Al/Cu 2-ply composites, (b) fracture macrostructure for 2-ply tensile specimens.

Mechanical properties such as tensile strength and elongation of the bimetallic Al-Cu sheets and those of monolithic parent pure copper and AA 1050 alloy are displayed in Fig. 3. It is interesting to note here that the tensile strength of the two-ply composite reduces slightly as the reduction ratios decreases. The tensile strength of the two-ply laminate can be calculated by the typical rule of mixture (ROM) as follows:

$$\sigma = f_{Al}\sigma_{Al} + f_{Cu}\sigma_{Cu} \quad (1)$$

where f and σ are the volume fractions and tensile strengths of the constituent alloys, respectively. Here, f can be substituted by the thickness for every constituent alloy assuming that the thickness of each alloy is homogeneous in the unidirectional tensile direction. It is clear that the calculated σ_{ROM} (solid triangle) is in good agreement with the experimental one (solid reverse triangle). It is also interesting to note here that the elongation up to the initiation of necking as well as fracture is increased with the reduction ratio. This implies that plastic deformation of the less-ductile Cu in sample #1 is somewhat stabilized against necking or is retarded from interface delamination parallel to the tensile axis, by the generation of the metallurgically bonded diffusion layer adjacent to the ductile counterpart such as the Al alloy.

Fig. 3. Variation in the tensile strength and elongation for both the two-ply composite and constituent Al and Cu sheets.

Fig. 4(a) shows the bonding strength as a function of displacement measured by roller drum-type peel test (standard ASTM D3167). Average bonding strengths for samples #1, #2 and #3 could be determined as 13.4 N/mm, 7.6 N/mm, and 0.10 N/mm in order. This indicating that for reduction ratios above 50%, there is a drastic improvement in bonding strength. This may be attributed to two factors: The first one is the interface microstructure. According to Chen [5], major cracks between Al/Cu joints generally propagate through the path near Al-side IMCs like Al_2Cu , $AlCu$, and Al_3Cu_4 , whose overall thickness are above $\sim 2 \mu m$. However, the solely generation of thinner Al_4Cu_9 IMC layer (thickness below 100 nm) without the aforementioned harmful Al-side IMCs can provide a strong metallurgical bonding between Al and Cu for two-ply sample #1, as shown in Fig. 1(a).

Fig. 4. (a) True stress-strain curves for Al/Cu 2-ply composites, (c) plots of the bonding strength versus the peeling distance.

The other factor is an actual bonding area at the Al/Cu joint. In order to verify the relationship between actual contact surface area and bonding strength, separated surfaces of the representative samples after the peel tests were observed from the positions marked in Fig. 4(b) by SEM. Fig. 5

exhibits surface microstructures of peel tested specimen from aluminum side. With increasing reduction ratios above 50%, both the length and density of vein cracks increased, indicating a ductile fracture process. On the other hand, the fraction of vein cracks was noticeably decreased and the region of brittle shear was considerably widened at the joint surface of peel-tested Al in Al/Cu laminate fabricated with a 30% reduction ratio. The reduced lengthy vein patterns together with the generation of brittle shear are consistent with the hypothesis that decreasing reduction ratio will reduce the fraction of actual strong bonding area at joints between dissimilar metals [6].

Fig. 5. Fractographs observed from Al surfaces of peel-tested specimens.

Backscattered electron SEM observations were also employed to observe peel-tested surfaces of Cu side (Fig. 6). EDS analysis revealed the presence of pure aluminum (dark part). According to Hosseini [7], local metallurgical bonding actually took place in this region. Fig. 7 plots the variations in the average bonding strength and actual bonding area with respect to the reduction ratio, where actual bonding area is obtained by measuring the fraction of dark area in Fig. 6 from the Cu part that is observed using iSolution DT image analyzer. It can be observed that the increase in the reduction ratio above 50% leads to a drastically improved actual bonding area

because of the high stress concentrations at joints that might be responsible of the increase in the average bonding strength.

Fig. 6. BSE SEM micrographs showing fracture morphology obtained from the peeling surfaces of Cu alloy.

Fig. 7. Variation of bonding strength and actual bonding area as a function of reduction ratios.

Since flexural strength is one of the most important mechanical properties directly related to interface delamination, standard three-point bending test has to be done. After preparing rectangular specimens 10 mm in width and 55 mm in length, 3-point bending tests were performed for the Al-Cu 2-ply sheets under a constant deformation rate of 5 mm/min. Fig. 8 illustrates the schematics of the 3-point bending tests for Al-Cu 2-ply sheets adopted in this study.

Fig. 8. Schematics of 3-point bending tests for Al-Cu 2-ply sheets.

Fig. 9(a) shows the flexural load-displacement curves for the samples #1, #2 and #3 for the case A indicating Al_{in}/Cu_{out} (i.e., aluminum layer is located inside the bent clad). The initial bending characteristic can be further zoomed and presented in three distinguished stages as shown in Fig. 9(b). In the stage I of Fig. 9(b), the rate of stress increases upon displacement. Further loading causes a linear load-displacement relationship, conformed to stage II of Fig. 9(b). Finally plastic deformation of the 2-ply clad sheet started in the stage III of Fig. 9(b). Here the upper transition stress (σ_{uts}) can be determined as indicated in Fig. 9(b). For the case A, σ_{uts} values for the samples #1, #2 and #3 were determined as 510.7, 431.8 and 403.4 MPa, respectively. This implies that the higher applied load was required for the plastic deformation of roll bonded Al-Cu 2-ply sheets fabricated under higher reduction ratio. Flexural strengths for the samples #1, #2 and #3 were 783.6, 719.5 and 721.6 MPa, respectively. Maximum flexural strength was observed for the 2-ply sheet fabricated under the highest reduction ratio of 65% adopted in this study. However, bending deformation behavior of the sheets roll bonded under the reduction ratio below 50% is quite similar.

Fig. 9. (a) Displacement-effective stress curves of roll-bonded Al/Cu 2-ply composites in bending case A indicating Al_{in}/Cu_{out} (i.e., aluminum layer is located inside the bent clad) (b) Initial stage of displacement-effective stress curve from Al/Cu 2-ply composite roll bonded under 65% of reduction ratio.

Fig. 10 exhibits the flexural load-displacement curves for the samples #1, #2 and #3 for the case B indicating Cu_{in}/Al_{out} (i.e., copper layer is located inside the bent clad). Here σ_{uts} values for the samples #1, #2 and #3 were determined as 581.4, 440.4 and 434.6 MPa, respectively. Also flexural strengths for the samples #1, #2 and #3 were 820.6, 586.8 and 581.4 MPa, respectively. For the samples subjected to higher reduction ratio above 50%, a significant increase in both the upper transition and flexural stresses is observed, presumably attributed to the generation of a metallurgical bonding layer between Al and Cu with a thickness around ~ 70 nm.

Fig. 10. Displacement-effective stress curves of roll-bonded Al/Cu 2-ply composites in bending case B indicating Cu_{in}/Al_{out} (i.e., copper layer is located inside the bent clad)

Fig. 11 exhibits cross-sectional FE-SEM images of the bending-induced interface microstructure of Al_{in}/Cu_{out} 2-ply samples. For the sample #1, there is no sign of the abrupt interface delamination perpendicular to the loading direction. Instead, homogeneously distributed voids with the size of several-hundred nm diameters were observed at interface between parent Cu and Al alloys. Interestingly, crack propagation was obviously retarded and multiple shear bands were propagated in the direction of 45° from the loading axis. On the other hand, relatively large voids were inhomogeneously generated at interface between parent Cu and Al for the 2-ply sheets fabricated under the reduction ratio below 50%. Adjacent to these voids, several lateral cracks with the size of ~ 5 μm were developed toward the loading direction. And the macroscopic delamination perpendicular toward the loading direction at Cu-Al interface was clearly observed.

Cross-sectional FE-SEM images after 3-point bending for the Cu_{in}/Al_{out} 2-ply samples were shown in Fig. 12. Similar to the case A (Al_{in}/Cu_{out}), a lot of fine voids were generated at interface, which were homogeneously distributed. However, for the samples roll bonded at reduction ratio below 50%, both longitudinal delamination and lateral crack propagation can be observed at interface between parent Cu and Al alloys.

Fig. 11. FE-SEM images after 3-point bending tests showing Al/Cu interface microstructure for case A.

Fig. 12. FE-SEM images after 3-point bending tests showing Al/Cu interface microstructure for case B.

4 Conclusions

The influence of reduction ratio on the microstructure evolution at interface and subsequent mechanical properties of roll-bonded Al/Cu 2-ply clad metal was investigated in this study. By using

TEM, nm-order of interface diffusion layer was observed in the interface of sample #1, implying metallurgical bonding seemed to be progressed during roll bonding under the reduction ratio of 65 %. On the other hand, the development of the phases or voids in the interface controls the mechanical properties of the Al/Cu 2-ply composites. After carrying out both uniaxial tensile and peel tests, we can conclude that sample #1, the highest reduction ratio of 65 % adopted in this study, exhibited excellent mechanical properties in terms of tensile strength, elongation and peel strength.

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